

NEW METHODS MODELING PROBLEMS DIGITAL PROCCECING SIGNALS

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Abstract. Computer vision as a scientific discipline refers to the theories and technologies for creating medical database systems that receive information from an image. Despite the fact that this discipline is quite young, its results have penetrated almost all areas of life. Computer vision is closely related to other practical areas like image processing, the input of which is two-dimensional images obtained from a camera or artificially created. This form of image transformation is aimed at noise suppression, filtering, color correction and image analysis, which allows you to directly obtain specific information from the processed image. This information may include searching for objects, feature points, segments, etc. All scalar processors operate in SIMD mode, while executing a block of threads in the G80, the number of threads in a block is 32, called a warp. At the same time, in 4 clock cycles of the multiprocessor, all beam streams are processed at once when performing operations with floating point, with double precision - in 32 clock cycles, and transcendental functions - in 16 clock cycles. The number of threads per multiprocessor is limited. To synchronize the threads, special instructions have been developed that interrupt the execution of a bundle and start the next bundles in the queue until all bundles are interrupted.

Key words: Grafic processors, algorithm, memory, hardware, software.

Introduction.

The basis of the search for objects in the image using the Viola-Jones method is the Haar features of a rectangular shape. Computing one such feature in OpenCV requires finding three rectangle intensities multiplied by a weighting factor:

$$h = \sum_{t=1}^3 \alpha_t \cdot ii_t \tag{1}$$

The coordinates of the rectangles for a sliding window of minimum size are set when training a cascade of classifiers. Let the dimensions of the sliding window be defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} w' &= f^i \cdot w_0 \\ h' &= f^i \cdot h_0 \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

here w_0 and h_0 - minimum (initial) dimensions of the sliding window;

f - window scaling factor;

i - iteration at which the window dimensions are calculated, while the maximum iteration is equal to:

$$i_{\max} = \text{ceil} \left(\min \left(\log_f \frac{w+1}{w_0}, \log_f \frac{h+1}{h_0} \right) \right) \tag{3}$$

To calculate the intensity of one rectangle by the integral, you need to know the values of the integral in 4 pixels (see Fig. 1). Thus, to calculate the intensity of one rectangle, 3 addition / subtraction operations, one multiplication are required, and to calculate the entire Haar sign, 11 addition / subtraction operations and 3 multiplication operations.

$$ii = ii_1 + ii_2 - ii_3 - ii_4$$

Fig.1. Determination of the intensity of the image rectangle by its integral

Further, the Haar signs form a cascade that already determines whether the object is in the specified area or not. In OpenCV, when training a cascade, each Haar feature has its own response threshold, at which one or another value is added to the sum of the cascade depending on the value of the feature (in this case, the threshold value itself is multiplied by the light correction factor [1,3,11]):

$$s = \sum_{c=1}^{c_{\max}} \begin{cases} h_c < thres_c \cdot l, a1_c \\ h_c \geq thres_c \cdot l, a2_c \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

where the values $a1_c, a2_c, thres_c, c_{\max}$ are determined when training a cascade of classifiers, as well as weights in the classifiers themselves. Thus, to calculate the cascade of classifiers, it is necessary to execute $12 \cdot c_{\max}$ additions, $4 \cdot c_{\max}$ multiplications and $c_{\max}$ comparisons. Then this sum is compared with the threshold value of the cascade, and if it is greater than it, then it is concluded that the cascade has detected the object. The sequence of such cascades makes it possible to identify complex objects in the image. If for $c_{\max}$ accept the total number of Haar features in all cascades, then in total they require $21 \cdot c_{\max}$ flop (provided that one multiplication requires 2 flop additions). Then the total number of operations required to detect an object by the integral of the image, provided that an object is detected in each pixel, can be estimated by the following formula:

$$W_s(N) = \sum_{i=0}^{I-1} (w - f^i \cdot w_0 + 1) \cdot (h - f^i \cdot h_0 + 1) \cdot (21 \cdot c_{\max}) \quad (5)$$

It is clear that this situation will not occur on real images, but nevertheless, an estimation of the algorithm execution time for the CPU is necessary in order to find out whether it is expedient to execute the algorithm on the central processor:

$$T_{CPU}(N) = \frac{W_s(N)}{S_{CPU}} \quad (6)$$

Graphs of the theoretical and experimental time estimates are shown in fig. 2. (sliding window size $w_0 = 24$ на $h_0 = 24$, scaling factor $f = 1.2$, $c_{\max} = 2913$ classifiers). In an

image with dimensions of 1024 by 1024, 637 possible areas of the object were found in total. That is why the graph of the experimental evaluation is much lower than the theoretical one, because In practice, the number of positive search results for objects in the image is very small compared to the number of sliding windows processed, and it is impossible to predict the number of found objects in advance. However, in order to compare the performance of algorithms, it is necessary to calculate the maximum possible estimate of the execution time, i.e. such that all pixels of the image (each sliding window) will be considered as possible areas for finding the object. It is it that displays the peak performance of the algorithm under consideration.

The multilevel memory hierarchy allows access to global data through the first and second level caches. The second level of the cache is shared between data and texture units, while the first level is shared between the two multiprocessors and is intended for data only. When calculating on a multiprocessor, in addition to data from global memory, two additional types of memory are used: constant memory and shared memory. The constant memory is read-only. It is stored in video memory and cached on the 8 KB multiprocessor (the total size for all multiprocessors is limited to 64 KB; the constant memory is the same for all multiprocessors). The latency when accessing it can be the same time as for accessing global memory in case of a cache miss, but if there is a cache hit, then the access will be performed in 2 multiprocessor clock cycles [5]. Shared memory is intended for reading / writing and is organized in the form of memory banks (16 or 32), each of which can be accessed in 2 clock cycles. The entire bundle gets the request to access the shared memory[11]. In this case, requests may arise immediately to one bank of shared memory, which will entail a conflict and ordering of requests into the queue with an increase in the access time to bank data for the entire bundle. Therefore, it is important to take into account the coherence of requests when creating algorithms [1]. The amount of shared memory is also limited (16 KB), but in later versions of GPUs (Compute Compatibility 2.x) it can be configured depending on the task. In the process of studying various types of access to memory caches, it was revealed that the required number of cycles can vary significantly [10].

The device that is the main one in the computing system (CPU) is called the Host. It runs the main sequential program, which transfers control to the parallel computing device Device (GPU) to implement parallel computations. The program that Device runs is called the Kernel. The kernel is developed in the same language in which the sequential program (C / C++) is

implemented using special language additions. Parallel execution on a Device is implemented due to threads combined into blocks. The blocks, in turn, are combined into a (Grid) section, which must completely cover the data processed by the kernel. In order for the Device to process any data, it is necessary to transfer it to the Device memory, then get the result by copying the data in the opposite direction.

PRAM (Parallel Random Access Machine) is an idealized abstract model of a synchronous shared memory machine. This model was proposed in 1978 by S. Fortune and J. Wyllie [5] to estimate the performance (in particular, the execution time) of parallel algorithms.

PRAM assumes the presence of an infinite number of processors, each of which can synchronously execute various instructions on data in a shared memory, thus operating in MIMD mode [2]. If all processors execute the same instructions, then this model can be considered an abstract SIMD machine. The PRAM model does not consider the problems of synchronization and communication of processors, and the main instructions that processors can execute are the same as those of a conventional RAM (Random Access Machine, a machine with random access to memory) [9]: arithmetic, logical operations, and memory access operations. The latter cause a number of problems in parallel algorithms, therefore, within the framework of the PRAM model, several different strategies have been developed to resolve memory access conflicts:

- 1) the number of processors in the machine is not limited;
- 2) each processor has equal access to any cell of the shared memory;
- 3) the size of the shared memory is not limited;
- 4) there is no competition for resources;
- 5) processors operate in MIMD mode.

To simulate algorithms on a PRAM machine, emulators were created that reflect the main features of this model [9].

To model and analyze algorithms on PRAM, it is necessary to represent their calculations in the form of an acyclic directed graph “operations-operands” [1]:

$$G = (V, R)$$

V where is the set of graph vertices representing the operations of the algorithm;

R is the set of graph arcs.

Objective Statement

Obviously, not all computer vision algorithms can be parallelized on GPUs. Any artificial computer vision system, regardless of its area of application, should include the following typical

stages of work:

- 1) image acquisition (photo or video filming);
- 2) preliminary processing;
- 3) highlighting characteristic features;
- 4) detection or segmentation;
- 5) high-level processing.

One of the basic features of orthogonal bases is presence of fast algorithms for definition of spectral factors. Fast algorithms allow to reduce quantity of arithmetic operations and volume of necessary memory. The increase in speed is as a result reached at use of orthogonal bases for digital processing signals [1, 2, 3, 4].

Materials nad Methods Bulk Synchronous Parallel (BSP, Valiant, 1990) is an extension of the PRAM model [8]. Later it was transformed into a parallel computing standard [6]. In this model, the main attention is paid to communication and synchronization of processors. Therefore, the model consists of the following components [7]:

- 1) Processors, each of which has fast local memory and can execute multiple virtual threads;
- 2) A communication network that allows sending and receiving communication messages from processors;
- 3) A mechanism for synchronizing all processors at certain points in time.

The algorithm in BSP has a vertical and horizontal structure [10]. The vertical structure is a sequence of supersteps, each of which consists of three main steps:

- 1) Local calculations on each processor using only the data that was stored in the processor's local memory.

Unlike the G80, the multiprocessor in the R600 does not have a local shared memory, but consists of a certain number of vector processors. It is the number of vector processors that determines the size of a bunch of processes (wavefront - in ATI's terminology). In the best configuration, one multiprocessor included 16 vector ones. Each vector processor consists of four scalar processors, one transcendental function processor, a branch block and general purpose registers. Thus, at one time, due to the use of VLIW, five operations on 32-bit numbers can be simultaneously performed on one vector processor. But most general-purpose parallel

computing emphasizes scalar computing, so this parallelization feature is rarely used. Different VLIW commands can be executed on all multiprocessors, but on one multiprocessor for all vector processors, the instruction must be the same, but with different address registers. Access to video memory is performed for all threads simultaneously within 300 to 600 multiprocessor cycles [6], but due to the use of VLIW and scheduling of thread bundles, the delay in accessing the global memory of the video adapter is effectively hidden.

The memory controller reports to the task manager. Processed data and constant memory are stored in video memory and, if necessary, cached in caches of the second and first levels, while they are common to all multiprocessors.

The architecture of the latest generation R800, presented in September 2009 [7], is almost identical to the R700. The changes mainly affected the quantitative characteristics:

- 1) the size of the shared memory of the multiprocessor has been increased to 32 KB;
- 2) increased the number of multiprocessors to 20 in the best configuration.

ATI Stream SDK and the OpenCL language, which uses its own heterogeneous model [1, 8], are used to program ATI GPUs. Unlike CUDA, this model is applicable not only to data parallelism, but also to task parallelism, and takes into account the number of CPU cores. OpenCL is based on a C-like language for writing program cores.

Results and Discussion

The models of parallel programming discussed above are intended primarily for the programmer to have an idea about the main structural elements of graphic processors, which include memory and computing elements, and the relationships between them. In addition, both CUDA and OpenCL have some algorithm abstraction that assumes that input and output data are represented as an array of elements, each of which is processed independently of each other, due to which data parallelism is achieved. We highlight the main disadvantages of these models:

- 1) there is no mathematical description of the abstract model of the GPU, so it is impossible to estimate the running time of a particular algorithm on different GPUs;
- 2) significant parameters of parallel algorithms have not been identified, thanks to which it is possible to analyze and compare these algorithms in terms of execution time on a GPU with a certain configuration;
- 3) despite the fact that the models are heterogeneous (i.e. they take into account not only

graphics processors, but also central ones), they do not have methods for making a decision about the target computing system;

4) for these models, general principles for optimizing parallel computing have not been developed (in [2, 6], optimization methods are given for a specific platform, but not for a model);

5) there is no general methodology for the development of parallel algorithms.

These shortcomings are associated with a number of factors that one has to face when developing a parallel computing model [9], the main of which is the lack of a formal parallel computing model using a central and graphic processor. A formal model is provided by all abstract models of parallel computing with their abstract machines, but it is quite difficult to find a formal model suitable for analyzing parallel computing on GPUs due to the diversity of their architectures. Nevertheless, there are attempts to formalize some aspects of parallel computing on GPUs.

Conclusions

If the GPU is the Device, then the size of the partition and blocks is limited. Each block is executed on a separate multiprocessor independently of other blocks. Therefore, the width and height of the block are determined by the maximum number of simultaneously processed threads on the multiprocessor. In turn, when executed, the blocks are divided into bundles of 32 threads, which are launched in accordance with the commands of the multiprocessor thread control unit. Communication between threads in a block is done using shared memory and barrier thread synchronization. Series of numerical experiments have been carried out on the research of piecewise-quadratic bases.

The numerical experiments allow us to draw a conclusion that the number of zero coefficients at digital processing of signals received as a result of bench tests in Walsh and Haar's piecewise-quadratic bases ranges from 5 % up to 17 %, when processing the geophysical signals received as a result magnetic exploration we get values ranging from 5 % up to 25 %, and while processing elementary functions (and also functions consisting of their combinations) this parameter gives us value from 10 % up to 70 % with an accuracy of 10^{-4} - 10^{-6} . It is established, that decomposition (4) allows receiving high speed in Haar's basis and the big factor of compression in Walsh's basis. Also as a result of researches it is revealed, that with increase in quantity of readout function N , the values of factors decreases on exponential law.

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